

THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN THE METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of critical thinking in the methodological preparation of future history teachers in the system of continuous education.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, skillful analysis, intellectual process, didactics, weak and strong critical thinking, didactic method.*

РОЛЬ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ИСТОРИИ В СИСТЕМЕ НЕПРЕРЫВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается роль критического мышления в методической подготовке будущих учителей истории в системе непрерывного образования.*

Ключевые слова: *критическое мышление, умелый анализ, интеллектуальный процесс, дидактика, слабое и сильное критическое мышление, дидактический метод.*

INTRODUCTION

The criticality of information perception is especially relevant in the modern conditions of the political and economic situation in the world. The basis of critical thinking is personal property, such as a person's attitude to particular historical, political and social facts and events. The main knowledge and attitude to it lies in the process of family upbringing and education. Based on the specific characteristics of the activity, it plays an important role in the critical perception of information among future teachers of history and social studies in the continuing education system. Special training of future history teachers is necessary to fulfill this task.

Critical thinking is a high-level component of knowledge acquisition and independent thinking, and it is a mental phenomenon that expands a person's ability to objectively perceive events, events, and existence. In critical thinking, ideas and their importance are examined from the perspective of diversity and compared to other ideas. It emphasizes analysis, comparison, interpretation, innovation, problem solving, and inspires students to believe that creative ideas can triumph over bad ideas [7].

The development of a methodology for the formation of critical thinking in future history teachers in the continuous education system requires the study of several aspects:

- critical thinking of the teacher (future history teacher);
- correct presentation of information to students by future history teachers (emotionally diverse, but in a way that does not affect the personal attitude of students);
- formation of critical thinking among students by future history teachers.

First, it is necessary to define the concept of "critical thinking" based on the analysis of different definitions:

- some authors understand critical thinking as "the system of judgments used in the analysis of objects and phenomena and the formation of conclusions that allow rational evaluation and application of these results to other problems and situations."

- other researchers define critical thinking as "one of the ways of thinking in which a

person questions the received information”.

- There is a point of view of "critical thinking - correct assessment of various statements".
- another general definition of critical thinking is “conscious reflexive thinking aimed at making decisions: what to do and what to believe”;
- there is a detailed definition – “active and skillful analysis, intellectual process, conceptualization, application, synthesis of information obtained or produced by observation and/or evaluation, reflection or communication as a guide for experience, persuasion and action” [4].

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

In Farabi's works, didactic issues, theoretical problems of education, philosophical, physiological and psychological foundations of knowledge acquisition are widely considered. For him, the interaction between the object and the subject, the complex physiological and psychological processes of the person and the rich spiritual world are important. In particular, according to the scientist, the highest level of human spirituality is the soul, mind and thinking, which are manifested in specific forms characteristic of human critical thinking. Farabi developed a number of important recommendations on the organization of critical thinking. According to him, three things are necessary to be a good supervisor:

- 1) it is necessary to know well all the principles underlying a certain science;
- 2) it is necessary to be able to draw the necessary conclusions from these principles and information about this specific science, that is, it is necessary to master the rules of discussion;
- 3) to distinguish truth from lies and to correct errors, it is necessary to refute erroneous theories and analyze the opinions of other authors [3].

Tools that form critical thinking appear as a system only when the selection is made, taking into account the specific goals of each stage in the educational process, and they together affect each component of the critical thinking of future history teachers. The content of critical thinking is connected through three external factors: object, purpose, didactic principles development [2].

RESEARCH RESULTS

Researcher Richard Paul proposed to divide critical thinking into two types: strong and weak. Critical thinking in a weak sense is the thinking of a highly skilled professional with a quasi-intellectual egocentric motivation. That is, such a person is concerned only with personal well-being and does not think about the consequences of the moral nature of his actions for other participants in the relationship. The owner of this mindset often has a high level of education, but uses his knowledge to pursue unfair and selfish goals. In a strong sense, critical thinking is the thinking of a certain person who aims to get to the heart of the problem and study it objectively [5].

According to research psychologist Diana Halpern, critical thinking is the use of cognitive methods that are characterized by a high degree of control, validity, and purpose, and that increase the likelihood of obtaining the desired result. These techniques are used to solve problems, form inferences, estimate probabilities, and make decisions that require skills that are reasonable and effective for a particular type of task or situation.

Analyzing the above, the critical thinking of future history teachers in the continuing education system can be called a way of thinking, in which a person asks for incoming

information, analyzes it based on a system of personal knowledge, decisions and principles, makes reasonable conclusions and makes reasonable evaluations and comments.

By the external side of critical thinking, we understand the stimulation of much simpler processes (reception, attention, etc.) and the preservation of the general working ability of the individual. The following methods are used for this:

- to ensure the activation of the work of different nerve centers by sequencing different methods, types and methods of educational work;
- correct relationship between words and visuality, concrete and abstract in the educational process;
- moments of physical and musical rest in the lesson;
- support of positive emotions;
- the use of games and competitions as a didactic method, the internal side of critical thinking is, first of all, to activate the students' thinking, and in primary groups, to stimulate their imagination and creativity [2].

DISCUSSION

Despite the general definition of the concept of "critical thinking", it is possible to identify the main features that distinguish it from other types of thinking: critical thinking is independent thinking; information is the starting point, not the end point, of critical thinking; knowledge helps a person to think critically; critical thinking begins with problem and question formulation; critical thinking focuses on reliable evidence; critical thinking is social thinking.

Critical thinking is the analysis of evidence to draw conclusions. There are several different definitions that involve a rational, skeptical, unbiased analysis or evaluation of evidence on complex topics and subjects. Critical thinking is thinking that enables students to be self-directed, self-disciplined, self-monitored, and self-developed. This strictly implies perfect conditions and their rational use. It requires effective communication and problem-solving skills, as well as overcoming local egocentrism and sociocentrism [8].

Thus, the concept of critical thinking is multi-component and includes the following components: observation, logical thinking, interpretation and analysis, drawing conclusions, and the ability to evaluate. Critical thinking is based on broad criteria of intelligence and knowledge: rationality, depth, accuracy, perspective, relevance, and fairness.

The specific features of the technology of forming critical thinking are that the educational process should be based on scientifically based examples of human interaction with information; the stages of technology: difficulty, understanding, reflection, should be provided in the continuous education system so that future history teachers can be flexible and adapt to a specific educational situation at any time; technology enables learning based on the principles of collaboration and self-reflection. The definition of technology does not imply an algorithm and mechanical execution, but a system of open strategies that determines the entire process of forming critical thinking.

The use of critical thinking technology will help to solve these problems and create conditions that will maximally stimulate the development of intellectual abilities of future history teachers. Critical thinking - the human concept of "critical thinking" is about looking for flaws. When we say: "He is very critical", it means that the person does not want to take anything with extreme insecurity. Nevertheless, in the educational tradition, this term is often associated not with the teacher, but with the high-level content of the educational process (it is

very important for the educational technology to develop critical thinking). It is worth worrying about the strength of students' knowledge in a given area, because this knowledge changes every year and sometimes becomes outdated before students can master it. The arrival of young people who can learn to work with information independently, who can independently improve their knowledge and skills in various fields, and who can acquire new knowledge if necessary, is very important for the economy, science and culture, which will be related to their whole conscious life.

Critical thinking is one of the types of human intellectual activity, which is characterized by a high level of perception, awareness, objectivity of approaching the surrounding information field. Features of conceptual approaches of this technology are as follows:

- the goal of education is not the amount of knowledge or the amount of information, but how the student is able to manage this information;

- search, adapt in the best way, find meaning in it, apply it in life;

- not acquiring "ready-made" knowledge, but applying personal knowledge born in the educational process;

- the communicative-activity principle of teaching ensures the dialogue mode of classes, the joint search for ways to solve problems, as well as "partnership" relations between the teacher and the audience;

- objective assessment of the positive and negative aspects of the perceived object.

Critical Thinking:

- show interest - use research methods;

- to ask questions;

- regular search for answers;

- determining the causes and consequences of the evidence;

- doubting generally accepted truths;

- development of ability to point of view and defend it, with logical arguments;

- pay attention to the arguments of the opponent and understand them logically.

Personal characteristics that allow you to use the opportunity of critical thinking. In order for the student to use his critical thinking, it is important to develop a number of qualities, among which D. Halpern distinguishes the following: Preparation for planning, flexibility, persistence, readiness to correct your mistakes, looking for compromise solutions. We can give the following answers to the question of what the technology of critical thinking gives to the teacher. First of all, it creates an atmosphere of openness and responsible cooperation in the audience. Forms the ability to use the educational model and system of effective methods that contribute to the development of critical thinking and independent thinking in the educational process and causes them to become practitioners who know how to competently analyze their own activities. In turn, what can critical thinking technology give to the teacher. Critical thinking technology fosters both communication and responsible collaboration. Working in the critical thinking technology system, the teacher ceases to be the main source of information and turns learning using technology methods into a collaborative and interesting search [6].

The development of technology for the development of critical thinking in future history teachers in the continuous education system should be aimed at solving the complex task:

at the same time, it is necessary to involve future history teachers in the educational process;

to increase the thinking process and ability of future history teachers, flexibility of thinking, ease of transition from one information to another;

build independently, create concepts;

to develop the ability to convey information to others, to learn to correct the received information, to understand and accept the point of view of other participants of interaction.

There is a classic technique for the formation of critical thinking based on the three-phase structure of the lesson: difficulty, understanding, reflection:

the first stage consists of updating existing knowledge, arousing interest in learning new information, setting personal educational goals for future history teachers;

the second stage is characterized by obtaining new information and connecting the information received by future history teachers with existing knowledge;

the third stage involves reflecting and creating new knowledge, as well as setting new learning goals for future history teachers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be noted that the role of critical thinking in improving the methodological training of future history teachers is important in the modern continuous education system. It also forms the ability of future history teachers to use a system of effective methods and a teaching model that contributes to the development of critical thinking and independent thinking in the educational process, and causes them to become competitive mature professionals who know how to competently analyze their work.

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